

D1.7 Sustainability Plan

115966 – PREFER

**Patient Preferences in
Benefit-Risk
Assessments during the
Drug Life Cycle**

**WP1 – Project
Management &
Communication**

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V0.3	31.01.2022	Integration of key future research areas of PREFER Recommendations' chapter 8
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V0.5	02.03.2022	Final Draft considering comments from SC members and from PREFER Recommendations chapter 8 team
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Introduction

The Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) is Europe's largest public-private initiative aiming to speed the development of better and safer medicines for patients. IMI supports this aim through collaborative research projects and building networks of industrial and academic experts in order to boost European pharmaceutical innovation.

In the IMI 2 Joint Undertaking, IMI has defined its Strategic Research Agenda health priorities to ensure the needs of patients are adequately addressed and, where appropriate, patient involvement is encouraged. Beyond the IMI agenda, there was an increasing recognition of the importance of incorporating patient needs and perspectives into decision making and to provide more avenues for patient engagement. While stakeholders were in agreement regarding the high value of patient input, an appropriate structured approach, including a set of systematic methodologies and recommendations for their use, were identified as needed for inclusion and engagement of patient perspectives during the development, approval, and post-approval phases. It was understood that this approach should accommodate the requirements of both Regulatory Authorities and other stakeholders, such as health technology assessment (HTA) bodies and reimbursement agencies. As Patient engagement was considered by all stakeholders as important, it was acknowledged that such complex questions remain in relation to the methods to elicit patient preferences and how to integrate findings into decision making.

Since 2016, PREFER looked at when and how it is best to perform and include patient preferences in decision making during the medical product life cycle. Patient stakeholders were included at every level of the project. The end-result are recommendations to support development of guidelines for industry, Regulatory Authorities and HTA bodies

PREFER objectives

The main objective of PREFER is to strengthen patient-centric decision making throughout the life cycle of medical products (a term which, in the context of this proposal, includes drugs, biologics, medical devices and vaccines) by developing expert and evidence-based recommendations to guide industry, Regulatory Authorities, HTA bodies and reimbursement agencies on when and how patient preference studies should be performed, and the results used to inform decision making.

The PREFER consortium defined the following goals (references: initial Description of Action (DoA) and a clarification document after the kick-off meeting in 2016 which has been agreed with IMI in May 2017):

- To determine when and how patient preferences may support decision making across the medical product life cycle and to ascertain which patient-preference elicitation methods are most promising to inform medical product decision making at different decision points in the drug life cycle for industry, Regulatory Authorities, HTA bodies and reimbursement agencies
- To design, execute, and evaluate case studies
- To generate recommendations on patient-preference elicitation to inform medical product decision making throughout the life cycle for industry, Regulatory Authorities, HTA bodies, and reimbursement agencies

PREFER achievements

The PREFER project achieved its objectives by delivering expert and evidence-based Recommendations on when and how to elicit patient preferences to inform medical product decision making throughout the life cycle and guide industry, Regulatory Authorities, HTA bodies, and reimbursement agencies.

The PREFER Recommendations are complemented by

- Experience from 10 case studies summarized in high-quality study protocols and reports, publications and webinars
- Operational Guidance including templates
- Training and Webinars
- Scientific peer-reviewed publications

These achievements are the result of a close collaboration of experts from academic research institutions, pharmaceutical companies, patient organizations, a health technology assessment body, and small and medium-sized enterprises within the PREFER consortium, and were developed based on stakeholder interviews and feedback, based on in depth preference methods review and the experience and results of prospective case studies as illustrated in Figure 1.

Furthermore, the PREFER Recommendations are complemented by a positive Qualification Opinion from EMA on

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the PREFER Framework and “Points to consider” for method selection along with five methods for performing patient preference studies to inform regulatory and HTA body medical product decision-making. Major parts of the PREFER Recommendations are based on the Briefing Book as submitted to EMA for the Qualification Opinion and thus, it is fair to say that the PREFER Recommendations are aligned with EMA’s current thinking.

Additionally, PREFER achieved a remarkable increase in knowledge, expertise and understanding of patient preference studies among the PREFER consortium members and collaborating stakeholders. In addition, six students received their PhD on patient preference research questions and contributed to PREFER with their own patient preference studies.

Finally, PREFER managed to present the work from all workpackages on an ongoing basis at clinical conferences (e.g. RA related conferences like EULAR, NMD related conferences), at scientific conferences and workshops (e.g. IAHP, ISPOR, HTAi, ICPE) and at conferences with relevance for specific stakeholders (e.g. TOPRA and DIA meetings in Europe and US which are well attended by regulators and more frequently by HTA bodies as well). PREFER engaged in stakeholder discussions at such conferences or workshops (e.g. DIA-PREFER workshop in 2021), or in individual meetings to discuss scientific or strategic questions (e.g. to get insights from patients on the interactions in patient preference studies or to get insights from regulators, HTA bodies and patients on the prioritization of methodological questions for the PREFER case studies).

Figure1: PREFER achievements to support future Patient Preference Research throughout the medical product lifecycle

PREFER impact assessment

While the patient perspective has been seen as important in medical product decision making over more than a decade, when PREFER started in 2016 there was a lack of guidance on when and how to capture patient preferences in a scientifically rigorous way.

The PREFER Recommendations, with its strong input from regulators and HTA bodies, now allow future sponsors of patient preference studies to design and execute the studies in a way that it addresses key aspects which are of high relevance for the stakeholders who intend to use the preferences for decision-making. Such key aspects include for example identification of situations when a preference study could add value for decision making, the selection of an appropriate preference method, early scientific advice from regulators and/or HTA bodies or

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reimbursement agencies to the study sponsor on the design of the study, and involvement of patient research partners into the study team. Thus, the PREFER Recommendations and other outputs build a strong foundation for scientifically rigorous future patient preference studies and bear a high likelihood of changing the practice of conducting patient preference studies including interactions between all stakeholders.

During the course of the PREFER project several stakeholders started or continued to develop research agendas, proposals or guidance to establish a patient-centric drug development, for example:

Stakeholder	Reference
<p>FDA: draft benefit-risk guidance includes section on the << Role of Patient Experience Data in FDA's Benefit-Risk Assessment>>. PDUFA VII: commitment letter includes section on <<Enhancing the Incorporation of the Patient's Voice in Drug Development and Decision-Making>>; FDA are writing 4 guidance documents on Patient-Focused Drug Development; CDRH have a guidance in place on the use of patient preference information in regulatory submissions</p>	<p>Benefit-Risk Assessment for New Drug and Biological Products FDA https://www.fda.gov/industry/prescription-drug-user-fee-amendments/pdufa-vii-fiscal-years-2023-2027 CDER Patient-Focused Drug Development FDA Center for Biologics Evaluation and Research Patient Engagement Program FDA Patient Preference Information (PPI) in Medical Device Decision-Making FDA</p>
<p>EMA: Regulatory Science Research Needs Initiative 2021 covers the topic of <<optimal approaches for patient input into the benefit-risk assessment in decision making>>; similar statement in the 2021 workplan.</p> <p>Qualification Opinion of IMI PREFER comprising a framework for patient preference studies and a 'points to consider' for method selection</p>	<p>EMA launches the Regulatory Science Research Needs initiative European Medicines Agency (europa.eu) https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/work-programme/chmp-work-plan-2021_en.pdf qualification-opinion-imi-prefer_en.pdf (europa.eu)</p>
<p>ICH Reflection Paper: Proposed ICH Guideline Work to Advance Patient Focused Drug Development. (Of note, this paper mentions that the timing of further ICH activities on this topic should take into account the timing of other activities such as IMI PREFER.)</p>	<p>ICH reflection paper – proposed ICH Guideline work to advance Patient Focused Drug Development (PFDD) (europa.eu)</p>
<p>CIOMS (COUNCIL FOR INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS OF MEDICAL SCIENCES): Working Group XI – Patient Involvement in Development and Safe Use of Medicines</p>	<p>https://cioms.ch/working-groups/working-group-xi-patient-involvement/</p>
<p>HTA: EUnetHTA21; Sweden (PP to supplement QALYs)</p>	<p>EUnetHTA 21 – EUnetHTA; Experience-Based Swedish TTO and VAS Value Sets for EQ-5D-5L Health States – PubMed (nih.gov)</p>
<p>Preference Research:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● HTA: ISPOR Patient Preferences Task Force and Quantitative Benefit-Risk (qBRA) Task Force ● HTAi Patient and Citizen Involvement Interest Group (PCIG) ● IAHPR 	<p>ISPOR – Using Patient Preferences to Inform Decision Making Webinars Health Technology Assessment International (HTAi) IAHPR International Academy of Health Preference Research</p>

Members of the PREFER consortium have been consulted or contributed to all above initiatives and it is likely that PREFER members will continue to be involved in ongoing activities and research projects. PREFER also expects that the PREFER Recommendations build a strong foundation for health authorities (e.g FDA, EMA) and HTA bodies when they develop guidance for their own employees.

The increase in knowledge, expertise and understanding of patient preference studies during the course of the PREFER project led to organizational changes in industry and to an increase of capabilities to run patient preference studies. In addition, an increased interest by other IMI projects such as imSAVAR, Screen4Care and HIPPOCRATES can be noticed.

Access to PREFER deliverables

The PREFER deliverables are placed in the public domain via several outlets. This includes many open-access publications, webinars and presentations at conferences, which will also ensure that the scientific impact is sustained beyond the life of this project.

Table 1 provides an overview of all main PREFER deliverables and how these can be accessed. A more detailed list is given in appendices 1 to 4 which also shows the submission of PREFER deliverables to IMI.

The main platform for open access of the PREFER deliverables is Zenodo (<https://www.zenodo.org/>). Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artefacts. For each submission, a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) is minted, which makes the stored items easily citable. (reference: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zenodo_on_January_16,_2022). The use of Zenodo for IMI project deliverables is supported by IMI.

Table 1: The PREFER deliverables are publicly available:

	Deliverable
	<p><u>PREFER Recommendations</u> on when and how to run patient preference studies with relevance for medical product decision making including the design, conduct and use of patient preferences by industry, regulators, HTA bodies/payers</p> <p>Public access: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6470922 The PREFER Recommendations in brief: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6470918</p>
	<p><u>EMA Qualification</u> on the PREFER Framework and “Points to consider” for method selection along with five methods for performing patient preference studies to inform regulatory and HTA body medical product decision-making.</p> <p>Public access: qualification-opinion-imi-prefer_en.pdf (europa.eu)</p>
	<p><u>Operational Guidance</u> providing research templates and guidance on documents needed for patient preference study design & conduct</p> <p>Public access: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6400553</p>
	<p><u>Training & Webinars</u> aiming to increase stakeholders’ familiarity on patient preference studies</p> <p>Public access: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397608</p>
	<p><u>Scientific peer-reviewed publications</u> on the PREFER project, on patient preference research, case studies and PREFER outputs</p> <p>Public access: a) https://www.imi-prefer.eu/publications/ b) https://explore.openaire.eu/search/advanced/research-outcomes?f0=relprojectid&fv0=corda_h2020::42695dacf04480f35d6e4c046353a580&type=publications&qf=false&sortBy=resultdateofacceptance,descending</p>
	<p><u>Additional PREFER research deliverables</u> outlining the rationale, methods, and results from 10 case studies conducted within the PREFER project including how to investigate preference study transferability https://imi-prefer.eu/case-studies/ and Appendix 3</p>

PREFER case studies’ secondary use of data and results

PREFER is promoting the principle of open science and research sharing through peer reviewed publications, which are a valuable source for further research. If researchers wish to use PREFER generated data and results for future

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research, the following process should be followed:

- Researchers contact the corresponding author of the respective PREFER case study publication
- Alternatively, the main contact person of the respective PREFER case study can be found in Table 4 of the PREFER D1.9 Data Management Plan (Appendix 1, link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6599930>)
- The PREFER case study contact person will bring a reasonable request forward to the study sponsor or case study steering committee, as applicable, for review and decision of the data sharing request.

The data and result sharing requests will be reviewed and decided upon on a case-by-case basis, applying all respective data protection rules and regulations, and respecting potential intellectual property rights.

PREFER sustainability

Sustainability goals

Applying PREFER's Recommendations in a systematic and sustainable way requires continued efforts after the end of the project.

PREFER defined three main sustainability goals:

1. Continue to communicate, disseminate, and educate Patient Preference Studies best practice
2. Increase the number of patient preference studies which build on the PREFER Recommendations and establish patient preference studies as an accepted tool to generate evidence supporting medical-product decision making
3. Continue to enhance the field of patient preference studies based on PREFER deliverables

1. Continue to communicate, disseminate, and educate Patient Preference Studies best practice

This means specifically,

- Enabling access and use of the PREFER guidance toolbox with its elements as listed in Table 1 by:
 - Extended access to the IMI PREFER website (www.imi-prefer.eu) for another 5 years until 31st May 2027 (see also appendix)
 - Open access via Zenodo.
 - Improved access via e.g. PFMD platform and/or EUPATI platform including the consideration of innovative digital platforms (ref PREFER Recommendations, chapter 8.3.2)
 - Continued sharing new information via newsletters, LinkedIn, etc
 - Continue registering new preference studies in HPSTR
- Continue registering new preference studies in HPSTR
- Connect with policy and advocacy groups; influence new policy guidance
- Share the PREFER guidances & material within each partner organization and with others, e.g. with vendors
- Continue organizing and participating in webinars, workshops and conferences about Patient Preference Studies
- Consider development and evaluation of formal training materials for different stakeholders in collaboration with patient research partners (ref PREFER Recommendations, chapter 8.3.2)

2. Increase the number of patient preference studies which build on the PREFER Recommendations and establish patient preference studies as an accepted tool to generate evidence supporting medical-product decision making

- Show how stakeholders use the proposed **PREFER framework** across the medicines development lifecycle and if adjustments may be useful. Relatedly, more research is needed on how best to incorporate results from patient preference information into regulatory documents and Marketing Authorisation Application (MAA) dossiers based on a more complete understanding about what tables or figures would be most useful for decision-makers (ref PREFER Recommendations, chapter 8.3.1)
- Show how patient preference studies can generate pre-competitive knowledge about patient-relevant endpoints
- Show how patient preference studies can inform development strategies, inform the selection of appropriate Patient Reported Outcomes (PROs) and Clinical Outcome Assessment (COAs) and feed into medical product decision making by regulators and HTA bodies
- Future patient preference studies could investigate the potential value of extending reporting standards of patient preference studies to describe patient and other stakeholder involvement more thoroughly (ref PREFER Recommendations, chapter 8.3.1)

Overall, it is key for all stakeholders to see an increasing number of studies over the next years, to exchange lessons learnt and to publish and register new preference studies.

3. Continue to enhance the field of patient preference studies based on PREFER deliverables

PREFER was able to provide a foundation on when and how to run patient preference studies but there are still questions that require additional experience or additional examination beyond this six-year project. Future research should involve collaboration between all stakeholders – including guidance from scientific societies, regulators and HTA bodies – to build upon the results from PREFER and increase the use and understanding of patient preference studies.

The PREFER Recommendations chapter 8 “Future Areas of Research” propose several research questions to be further investigated in the future.

These research questions are related to

- Patient and stakeholder involvement
- Elicitation methods
- Qualitative and Quantitative Transferability
- Educational Materials
- Measuring Relevant Psychological Constructs and Individual Differences
- Future Research not Studied in Initial Scope of PREFER like e.g.
 - Individual Preferences and Shared Decision-Making
 - Attribute Reference Library
 - Mapping Patient Preference Study Attributes to Clinical Outcome Assessments
 - Revealed Preferences
 - Uncertainty of Treatment Benefits and Harms

Sustainability approach

The achievement of PREFER’s numerous sustainability goals requires continued engagement and collaboration in future consortia and working groups of all stakeholders, ongoing interactions and discussions at conferences, workshops and meetings. This is likely to become an activity over many years.

The PREFER consortium decided to build an informal **PREFER Expert Network** with PREFER members and additional subject matter experts as well as interested stakeholders. At the end of the PREFER project in May 2022 there were about 20 volunteers who signed up for an initial work on a **White Paper** to outline the objectives of the PREFER Expert Network following PREFER’s sustainability goals as described above. This includes to define concrete actions and to identify potential collaborators for joint activities (e.g. PFMD, EUPATI, IHI PREFER PLUS, MDIC, Reagan Udall Foundation, etc). These potential collaborators will be invited to review the draft White Paper and to discuss collaboration models as some of the activities might require establishing Research Collaborations to secure intellectual property and funding. It is planned to publish the White Paper in a peer-reviewed and high-impact journal and to identify one objective to work on starting as soon as possible after May 2022 with anticipated delivery in early 2023.

The project manager, coordinator and project leader will continue meeting regularly over several months to oversee the tracking of any open publication activities after May 2022. However, the main responsibility will be with the main PREFER author and PREFER publication team.

The open access to the PREFER deliverables as listed in table 1 and in the appendices will allow any other patient preference study interest group (e.g. within ISPE, ISPOR, HTAi), consortium (e.g. new and ongoing IMI / IHI projects), preference researchers (e.g. IAHPR), preference study sponsors etc to pick up open research topics and support enhancing the field of patient preference studies.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CDRH	Center for Devices and Radiological Health
CIOMS	Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences
COA	Clinical Outcome Assessment
COPD	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease
DIA	Drug Information Association

DoA	Description of Action
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EUnetHTA	European Network of Health Technology Assessment
EULAR	European Congress of Rheumatology
FDA	Food and Drug Association
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
HTAi	Health Technology Assessment International
ICH	International Conference of Harmonization
IAHPR	International Academy of Health Preference Research
ICPE	International Conference of Pharmacoepidemiology
IHI	Innovative Health Initiative
IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative
ISPOR	International Society of Health Economics and Outcomes Research
MAA	Marketing Authorisation Application
MI	Myocardial Infarction
MM	Multiple Myeloma
NMD	Neuromuscular Disorders
PCIG	Patient and Citizen Involvement Interest Group
PE	Patient Engagement
PED	Patient Experience Data
PDUFA	Prescription Drug User Fee Act
PPS	Patient Preference Study
PFMD	Patient Focused Medicine Development
PRO	Patient Reported Outcomes
qBRA	Quantitative Benefit-Risk-Assessment
RA	Rheumatoid Arthritis
TOPRA	Professional Organization of Professionals in healthcare Regulatory Affairs
US	United States

Appendix

The following appendices provide a detailed list of all PREFER deliverables, which of the deliverables are submitted to IMI and the Zenodo links for open access. A list of all publicly accessible deliverables can also be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5767708>

Project Place has been used as project management platform during the course of the PREFER project. This platform is still available after the end of the PREFER project for another 3 years until May 31, 2025 and can be used by the PREFER Expert Network. Project Place will continuously be hosted by Uppsala University.

Case study reports will be stored on Zenodo as soon as case study manuscripts are published.

Appendix 1: PREFER Outputs (WP 1)

Deliverable	Submitted to IMI	Public access
D1.1 PREFER website	yes	www.imi-prefer.eu The PREFER website will be online for another 5 years after the end of the project, i.e. until 31 st May 2027. Funding for this support is provided by the University Uppsala. The contact for the website would be Josepine Fernow, Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics, Dept of Public Health and Caring Sciences, Uppsala University.
D1.2 Defining Key Performance Indicators	yes	none
D 1.3 & 1.6 & 1.9 Data Management Plan	yes	Link to D1.9: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6599930
D1.4 Dissemination and communication plan	yes	none
D1.5 Open workshop on preference elicitation	yes	none
D1.7 Sustainability Plan	yes	This document
D 1.8 Workshop on preliminary results	yes (DIA PREFER workshop on June 15&16, 2021)	https://www.diaglobal.org/en/conference-listing/meetings/2021/06/dia-imi-prefer-patient-preferences-workshop/presentation/
D1.10 Final Event	Yes (Recommendation event 28 April 2022)	None (Recording through YouTube channel will be published shortly after 31 May 2022)

Appendix 2: PREFER Outputs (WP 2)

Deliverable	Submitted and approved by IMI	Public access
D 2.1 Desires, expectations, concerns and requirements of stakeholders about methodologies for patient-preference elicitation and their use in making well-informed decisions regarding medicinal products	yes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5499904
D 2.2 Processes, conditions and contextual factors that influence the utility and role of patient preference studies	yes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5727430
D2.3 Identification of assessment criteria used at decision points throughout the medical product lifecycle	yes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5750113
D2.4 Report on methods for measuring patient benefit-risk preferences in medical treatment	yes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5727440
D2.5 Identification of educational and psychological feature methods	yes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5750154
D2.6 Characterising and appraising the methods	yes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5763873
D2.7 Identification of candidate methodologies and	yes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5763889

criteria to assess empirical case and simulation studies		
D 2.8 Determine research questions and assessment criteria for the preference studies used in the empirical case studies	yes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5763902
Task report 2.9 (A summary of Work Package 2)	Not applicable	
Publication on Simulation Studies (task report 2.10) (publication only)	Not applicable	

Appendix 3: PREFER Outputs (WP 3)

Deliverable	Submitted and approved by IMI	Public access
D 3.1 Preparation of research templates for the case studies	yes	Not applicable (covered by Operational Guidance 4.4)
D 3.2 Study protocols showing the mapping of research questions and candidate methodologies identified in WP 2 to concrete study designs	yes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5865307
D3.3 Report describing and assessing the historical case studies from industry	yes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6389861
D 3.4 Description of prospective case studies from industry	yes	Not applicable
D 3.5 Report of case study RA (preventive treatment)	yes	<p>Link to IAHRP's study registry HPSTR: https://hpstr.org/record/190184/001/040/entry</p> <p>Link to study protocol: http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-045851</p> <p>Link to plain language summary: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5744859</p> <p>Link to study report: <i>Will be accessible on zenodo after publication of the study</i></p>
D 3.6 Report of case study NMD	yes	<p>Link to IAHRP's study registry HPSTR: https://hpstr.org/record/190182/001/025/entry</p> <p>Link to study protocol: https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.16116.1</p> <p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34395923/</p> <p>Link to study report: <i>Will be accessible on zenodo after publication of the study</i></p>
D 3.7 Report of case study lung cancer	yes	<p>Link to IAHRP's study registry HPSTR: https://hpstr.org/record/190183/001/029/entry</p> <p>Link to study protocol: https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2021.689114</p> <p>Link to plain language summary: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6260511</p> <p>Link to study report: <i>Will be accessible on zenodo after publication of the study</i></p> <p>Link to study report on ProjectPlace: https://service.projectplace.com/pp/pp.cgi/r1410478409</p>
D 3.8 Report on additional case studies	yes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5865369
Case study on Rheumatoid arthritis: Treatment options	yes	See 3.8 above
Case study on Diabetes	yes	See 3.8 above
Case study on Multiple Myeloma	yes	See 3.8 above
Case study on Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)	yes	See 3.8 above
Case study on Chronic pain	yes	See 3.8 above
Case study on Myocardial infarction	yes	See 3.8 above
Case study on PAVING: Gene therapy in haemophilia	yes	See 3.8 above
D 3.9 Report assessing the outcomes of the case studies versus criteria from WP 2	yes	<i>Will be accessible on zenodo after publication</i>

D 3.10 Report assessing the extent to which results of case studies can be translated to other disease areas	yes	Will be accessible on zenodo after publication
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Appendix 4: PREFER Outputs (WP 4)

Deliverable	Submitted and approved by IMI	Public access
D 4.1 Final scope document for recommendations	yes	Not applicable
D 4.2 Final report on operational requirements for the conduct of case studies	yes	Not applicable
D 4.3 PREFER Recommendations	<i>Planned submission date: March 2022</i>	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6470922
D4.4 – Operational guide (OG) on best practice for conduct of patient preference studies List of templates: Protocol Protocol Synopsis Statistical Analysis Plan (SAP) Data Management Plan (DMP) Informed Consent Invitation to Participate Patient Information Form Study Report Plain Language Summary	<i>Planned submission date: March 2022</i>	1 page with all links to the templates https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6400553
D4.5 Summary report on training materials (TM) Including Links to all webinars	<i>Planned submission date: May 2022</i>	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397609
EMA Qualification	<i>Not applicable</i>	Qualification letter: qualification-opinion-imi-prefer_en.pdf (europa.eu) PREFER Briefing Book: CHMP & EUnetHTA parallel Scientific Advice: Qualification of a Framework and “Points to consider” for method selection along with five methods for performing patient preference studies to inform regulatory and HTA-body medical product decision-making (europa.eu)